

Pressure-Induced Quantum Phase Transition in Boron Doped Diamond Thin Film

S. Arumugam,^{1*} L. Govindaraj,¹ R. Thiyagarajan,² Dinesh Kumar,³ K. Sethupathi,⁴ G. Baskaran,⁵ M. S. Ramachandra Rao,³

1 Centre for High Pressure Research, School of Physics, Bharathidasan University, Tiruchirappalli 620024, Tamil Nadu, India

2 Post Graduate and Research Department of Physics, Srimad Andavan Arts and Science College (Autonomous), Tiruchirappalli 620005, Tamil Nadu, India

2 Department of Physics, Nano Functional Materials Technology Centre and Materials science Research Centre, Indian Institute of Technology Madras, Chennai 600036, Tamil Nadu, India

4 Department of Physics, Low Temperature Physics Laboratory, Indian Institute of Technology (IIT) Madras, Chennai 600036, Tamil Nadu, India

5 The Institute of Mathematical Sciences, C.I.T. Campus, Chennai 600 113, India

* Corresponding Author: sarumugam1963@yahoo.com

Diamond in the form of thin films possess negative electron affinity characteristics. Hence, it is one of the important elements for electronic applications such as microchip substrates, high-efficiency electron emitters, photodetectors, transistors etc [1]. Boron has the smaller atomic radius and has one less electron than the diamond.

By the increasing of boron in pure diamond film, a semiconductor - metallic - superconducting transition is observed at the various concentrations such as of 0.3×10^{21} , 0.5×10^{21} and $0.6 \times 10^{21} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ [2]. Moreover, the presence of one free electron-boron impurity in boron doped diamond may induce a kind of smallest scale energy, quantum level change. Here, we have investigated the magnetic property of high concentrated ($2.9 \times 10^{21} \text{ cm}^{-3}$) Boron doped Diamond under very low perturbations such as temperature region (10 to 2 K), pressure (up to ~ 1 GPa), magnetic field (up to 6000 Oe). The application of a small pressure of 0.05 GPa at 10 Oe introduces a new anomaly near the very low temperature, and it is termed as Quantum Phase Transition. While increasing of magnetic field under different pressures such as 0.05 GPa, 0.25, 0.5 and 0.9 GPa, the QPT is continued to exist till 110 Oe, 130 Oe, 140 Oe and 150 Oe respectively. *i.e.*, the pressure supports to enhance the QPT transition. By having these complete information, two dimensional phase diagrams (H-T), (P-T) and a three dimensional (P-H-T) phase diagram for BDD of our concentration is reported for the first time as shown in figure 3.

References:

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